

HyPowerGT Consortium

Project Newsletter #1

HyPowerGT

*HyPowerGT – Demonstrating a hydrogen-powered gas-turbine engine
fuelled with up to 100% H₂*

Six months passed since the official kick-off of HyPowerGT. The first General Assembly of the project took place at Baker Hughes premises in Florence, Italy on 18 and 19 January 2024. The event was split up into day 1 (Kick-off) and day 2 (Implementing the action), comprising several meetings:

- General Assembly meeting (with kick-off)
- The Executive Board meeting
- The Management Support Team meeting
- The Administrative briefing
- An intervention from the Project officer from Clean Hydrogen JU
- The Work packages presentations in the plenum
- And the Site visit to the Baker Hughes GT testing facility

Since the launch of HyPowerGT, the project coordinator SINTEF established a platform that

facilitates effective internal communication and by building a collaborative environment that fosters an integrative process within the consortium and prepared the implementation and the data management plan.

The main activities of project partners between Month 1 and 6 also covered Work Package 2 (“Modelling Dry Low Emissions H₂ combustion system”) and 4 (“Safety management and risk assessment”):

- Project partners cooperated in the collection of data on turbulent burning rate for high-pressure hydrogen flames.
- Baker Hughes and CERFACS exchanged information with reference to the task on De-risking simulations of H₂-operated gas-turbine engines.

Baker Hughes NovaLT™ 16 gas turbine, 100% H₂ ready ()*

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In the initial phase of the project, our Consortium also achieved substantial results in communication and dissemination:

- [HyPowerGT website](#) is now online
- The project's leaflet, poster, roll-up banner and public presentations are also completed and available on the website [at this link](#).

HyPowerGT in the media

Interview Egidio Pucci (Baker Hughes) and Thomas Indlekofer (SINTEF)

In the recent issue of ETN Quarterly Newsletter (June 2024), our partners briefly presented HyPowerGT scope and objectives, as well as the innovative solutions that our project aims to develop.

Click [HERE](#) for the
full interview!
(Pages 14-15)

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